

Modeling Affective Content of Music: A Knowledge Base Approach

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Abstract—The work described in this paper is part of a project that aims to implement and assess a computer system that can control the affective content of the music output, in such a way that it may express an intended emotion. In this system, music selection and transformation are done with the help of a knowledge base with weighted mappings between continuous affective dimensions (valence and arousal) and music features (e.g., rhythm and melody) grounded on results from works of Music Psychology.

The system starts by making a segmentation of MIDI music to obtain pieces that may express only one kind of emotion. Then, feature extraction algorithms are applied to label these pieces with music metadata (e.g., rhythm and melody). The mappings of the knowledge base are used to label music with affective metadata. This paper focus on the refinement of the knowledge base (subsets of features and their weights) according to the prediction results of listeners' affective answers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Music has been widely accepted as one of the languages of emotional expression. The possibility to select music with an appropriate affective content can be helpful to adapt music to our affective interest. However, only recently scientists have tried to quantify and explain how music expresses certain emotions. As a result of this, mappings are being established between affective dimensions and music features [14][8].

Our work intends to design a system that may select music with appropriate affective content by taking into account a knowledge base with mappings of that kind. Most psychology researchers agree that affect has at least two distinct qualities [13][16][3]: valence (degree of satisfaction) and arousal (degree of activation), so we are considering these 2 dimensions in the classification. Automated classification using machine learning approaches has the advantage of allowing one to perform classifications in a faster and more reliable way than manual classifications. We intend to improve the knowledge base by selecting prominent features and by defining appropriate weights. This is done, respectively, by using feature selection and linear regression algorithms.

The automatic selection of music according to an affective description has a great application potential, namely in entertainment and healthcare. On the one hand, this system can be used in the selection of soundtracks for movies, arts, dance, theater, virtual environments, computer games and other entertainment activities. On the other hand, it can be used in music therapy to promote an intrinsic well-being. The next section makes a review of some of the most relevant contributions from Music

Psychology and related works from Music Information Retrieval. Section III gives an overview of the system. Section IV presents the details of the experiment. Section V shows the experimental results. Section VI analyses the results, and finally, section VII makes some final remarks.

II. RELATED WORK

This work entails an interdisciplinary research involving Music Psychology and Music Information Retrieval. This section makes a review of some of the most relevant contributions for our work from these areas.

A. Music Psychology

Schubert [14] studied relations between emotions and musical features (melodic pitch, tempo, loudness, texture and timbral sharpness) using a 2 Dimensional Emotion Space. This study was focused on how to measure emotions expressed by music and what musical features have an effect on arousal and valence of emotions. Likewise, Korhonen [4] tried to model people perception of emotion in music. Models to estimate emotional appraisals to musical stimuli were reviewed [14][6] and system identification techniques were applied. Livingstone and Brown [8] provided a summary of relations between music features and emotions, in a 2 Dimensional Space, based on some research works of Music Psychology. Gabrielsson and Lindstrom [3] is one of these works, where relations between happiness and sadness, and musical features are established. Lindstrom [7] analysed the importance of some musical features (essentially melody, but also rhythm and harmony) in the expression of appropriate emotions.

B. Music Information Retrieval

Emotions detection in music can be seen as a classification problem, so the selection of the classifier model and the feature set are crucial to obtain good results. Van de Laar [17] compared 6 emotion detection methods in audio music based on acoustical feature analysis. Four central criteria were used in this comparison: precision, granularity, diversity and selection. Emotional expressions can be extracted from music audio [19]. The method designed by Wu and Jeng consisted in 3 steps: subject responses, data processing and segments extraction. From the results of this method, emotional content could be associated to musical fragments, according to some musical features like pitch, tempo and mode.

Fig. 1. System overview

Muyuan and Naiyao [10] made an emotion recognition system to extract musical features from MIDI music. Support Vector Machines were used to classify music in 6 types of emotions (e.g., joyous and sober). Both statistical (e.g., pitch, interval and note density) and perceptual (e.g., tonality) features were extracted from the musical clips. There are also models to recommend MIDI music based on emotions [5]. The model of Kuo et al., based on association discovery from film music, proposes prominent musical features according to detected emotions. These features are compared with features extracted from a music database (chord, rhythm and tempo). Then, the result of these comparisons is used to rank music and a list of recommended music is given according to 15 groups of emotions.

III. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The work described in this paper is part of a project that has the objective of implementing and assessing a computer system that can control the affective content of the music output, in such a way that it may express an intended emotion. The system uses a database of pre-composed music represented at a symbolic level. We intend to accomplish our objective in 2 stages. The first consists in the selection / classification of music by affective content and is the focus of this paper. The second stage will deal with the transformation of the selected music to approximate even further its affective content to an intended emotional description. These stages are done with the help of a knowledge base with weighted mappings between continuous affective dimensions (valence and arousal) and music features (e.g., rhythm and melody). Fig. 1 illustrates our system.

IV. DETAILS OF THE EXPERIMENT

The experiment here described follows a preliminary one [12], overcoming some of its limitations by using larger numbers of music files, listeners and music features. Fig. 2 presents an overview of different stages of our experiment. The process starts with the segmentation of MIDI music to obtain segments that may express only one kind of emotion (this method is described in detail in the

Fig. 2. Stages of the experiment

following paragraph). Then, feature extraction algorithms of third party software [9][2][15] are applied to label these segments with music metadata (e.g., rhythm and melody). The mappings of the knowledge base are used to label music with affective metadata. For the experiments with listeners, we used a test set of 96 musical pieces. These pieces were of western tonal music (film music), last, approximately, from 20 seconds to 1 minute, and were used for both training and validating the classifier. 80 different listeners were asked to label online each affective dimension of the musical pieces with values selected from the integer interval between 0 and 10 [0;10]¹. The obtained affective labels were used to refine the sets of features and corresponding weights in the knowledge base. This was done separately for the valence and arousal.

A. Music segmentation

The expression of emotions in music varies as a function of time [4]. To facilitate classification, it is very important to obtain segments of music that may express only one kind of affective content. Our segmentation module uses the Local Boundary Detection Model (LBDM) [1][2] to obtain weights based on the strength of music variations (pitch, rhythm and silence). These weights establish plausible points of segmentation between segments with different musical features that may reflect different affective content. We define a threshold to reduce the search space among the LBDM weights. This threshold is equal to $1.30 \cdot \text{mean}(\text{LBDM weights}) + 1.30 \cdot \text{standard deviation}(\text{LBDM weights})$. We obtain music chunks of different length with a minimum of notes $MinN$ and a maximum of notes $MaxN$. To segment, we start at the beginning of the MIDI file and look for a plausible point of segmentation that corresponds to the maximum weight between the beginning of MIDI file + $MinN$ and the beginning of MIDI file + $MaxN$. This process is repeated starting from the last point of segmentation until we come to the end of the MIDI file.

¹<http://student.dei.uc.pt/%7Eapsimoes/PhD/Music/smc08/index.html>

Fig. 3. Mean and standard deviations of the affective responses for valence and arousal

B. Selection and weighting of features

We examined 146 unidimensional features and 3 multidimensional ones that were categorized in 6 groups: instrumentation (20), texture (15), rhythm (39), dynamics (4), melody (68) and harmony (3). Special attention was devoted to new features and important ones from a preliminary experiment[12]: the importance (volume*time) of 13 MFCCs [17] of each sample used to synthesize musical instruments, the prevalence (by note or time) of specific groups and individual instruments, tempo, notes density, duration of notes, rhythmic variability, melodic complexity, number of repeated notes, prevalence of the most common melodic intervals, pitch classes and pitches, and mode (major or minor). Each feature was analysed for the affective dimensions with the help of the affective labels obtained for the test set and of information obtained from the literature [11]. This was done by applying the following feature selection algorithms: Genetic search, best-first and greedy stepwise [18].

With the subsets of features selected, some algorithms of linear regression were used to refine the weights of each feature. Linear regression, SMO regression and SVM regression [18] were tested. The results of the next section were obtained with SVM regression, because it was, generally, the approach that gave us the best results.

V. RESULTS

Fig. 3 shows the mean and standard deviation for affective responses obtained in the online questionnaire². Answers distant more than the mean ± 2 *standard deviation were discarded.

The importance of individual features in each group of features was established (represented as positive or negative between parenthesis in tables I and II). All the features presented in tables I and II have a correlation coefficient higher than 15% with the affective labels.

A. Valence

Table I presents prediction results by groups of features for valence. From this, we can infer that rhythmic (e.g, tempo, average note duration, variability of note duration and time between onsets), harmonic (e.g., key mode and key), melodic (e.g., climax position and melodic complexity), texture (e.g., spectral texture MFCC 4 and 6, and number of unpitched instruments) and instrumentation features (e.g., string ensemble fraction) are relevant to the valence of music.

We started by applying feature selection algorithms [18] to reduce the number of features and to improve classification results. From this a group of 26 features resulted. The correlation and determination coefficients for training on the whole set were, respectively, 89.37% and 79.86%. 8-fold cross validation of classification resulted in correlation and determination coefficients of, respectively, 81.21% and 65.95%. After this we selected manually the best group of features to know the most important features in the stage of selection, but also for the stage of transformation. From this a group of 5 features

Features	Cor. Coef.	Det. Coef.
Note Prevalence Muted Guitar (+)	36.99%	13.68%
Electric Instrument Fraction (+)	33.72%	11.37%
Note Prevalence Steel Drums (+)	33.21%	11.02%
Time Prevalence Marimba (+)	31.41%	9.86%
Note Prevalence Fretless Bass (+)	31.02%	9.62%
Note Prevalence Timpani (-)	26.76%	7.16%
Electric Guitar Fraction (+)	23.4%	5.47%
String Ensemble Fraction (-)	21.5%	4.62%
Note Prevalence Pizzicato Strings (-)	21.08%	4.44%
Orchestral Strings Fraction (-)	20.7%	4.28%
Note Prevalence Orchestral Harp (-)	20.37%	4.14%
Saxophone Fraction (+)	19.75%	3.9%
Note Prevalence English Horn (-)	19.69%	3.87%
Note Prevalence French Horn (-)	19.56%	3.82%
Note Prevalence Tenor Sax (+)	19.18%	3.68%
Note Prevalence Synth Brass 1 (+)	19.12%	3.65%
Note Prevalence Pad 3 (polysynth) (+)	18.66%	3.48%
Note Prevalence Bassoon (-)	18.49%	3.41%
Time Prevalence Acoustic Grand Piano (-)	16.71%	2.79%
Acoustic Guitar Fraction (+)	16.46%	2.71%
Note Prevalence Ocarina (-)	16.18%	2.62%
Note Prevalence Banjo (-)	16.18%	2.62%
Note Prevalence Flute (-)	16.16%	2.61%
Woodwinds Fraction (-)	16.12%	2.60%
Note Prevalence Tuba (-)	15.88%	2.52%
Note Prevalence Xylophone (+)	15.0%	2.25%
Note Prevalence Accordion (+)	15.0%	2.25%
Spectral Texture MFCC 4 (+)	22.89%	5.23%
Spectral Texture MFCC 6 (+)	22.45%	5.04%
Spectral Texture MFCC 7 (+)	20.85%	4.35%
Number of Unpitched Instruments (+)	20.27%	4.11%
Spectral Texture MFCC 8 (+)	17.64%	3.11%
Spectral Texture MFCC 12 (-)	17.14%	2.94%
Number of Pitched Instruments (+)	16.39%	2.69%
Relative Note Density of Highest Line (-)	15.55%	2.42%
Initial Tempo (+)	62.95%	39.63%
Average Note Duration (-)	49.92%	24.92%
Average Time Between Attacks (-)	48.72%	23.73%
Strength Strong. Rhythmic Pulse (-)	42.72%	18.25%
Variability of Note Duration (-)	42.41%	17.98%
Note Density (+)	40.99%	16.8%
Strength Two Strong. Rhythmic Pulses (-)	37.66%	14.18%
Variability of Time Between Attacks (-)	36.57%	13.37%
Number of Relatively Strong Pulses (+)	30.24%	9.14%
Distinct Rhythm Count (+)	29.03%	8.43%
Rhythmic Variability (-)	28.06%	7.87%
Strength Sec. Strong. Rhythmic Pulse (-)	25.58%	6.54%
Strongest Rhythmic Pulse (+)	20.71%	4.29%
Average Meter Accent Synchrony (+)	19.88%	3.95%
Polyrhythms (-)	18.66%	3.48%
Staccato Incidence (+)	15.05%	2.26%
Climax Position (+)	32.7%	10.69%
Average Melodic Complexity (+)	24.15%	5.83%
Interval Strong. Pitch Classes (+)	20.84%	4.34%
Dominant Spread (+)	20.83%	4.34%
Consecutive Identical Pitches (+)	18.42%	3.39%
Key mode (-)	43.86%	19.23%
Key (-)	37.79%	14.28%
Strong Tonal Centres (-)	17.43%	3.04%

TABLE I
BEST FEATURES OF EACH GROUP - VALENCE

Features	Cor. Coef.	Det. Coef.
Electric Instrument Fraction (+)	28.48%	8.11%
String Ensemble Fraction (-)	27.79%	7.72%
Note Prevalence English Horn (-)	26.15%	6.84%
Number of Unpitched Instruments (+)	25.56%	6.53%
Note Prevalence Flute (-)	25.09%	6.29%
Brass Fraction (+)	25.0%	6.25%
Note Prevalence Orchestra Hit (+)	22.97%	5.28%
Electric Guitar Fraction (+)	21.5%	4.62%
Woodwinds Fraction (-)	21.08%	4.44%
Saxophone Fraction (+)	20.78%	4.32%
Percussion Prevalence (+)	20.75%	4.30%
Note Prevalence Tremolo Strings (+)	19.52%	3.81%
Note Prevalence Orchestral Harp (-)	18.96%	3.59%
Note Prevalence Electric Bass (finger) (+)	18.9%	3.57%
Time Prevalence Acoustic Guitar (nylon) (-)	17.79%	3.16%
Spectral Texture MFCC 2 (+)	28.16%	7.93%
Variability of Unpitched Instruments (+)	25.86%	6.69%
Spectral Texture MFCC 4 (+)	24.82%	6.16%
Melodic Intervals in Lowest Line (-)	18.99%	3.61%
Relative Range of Loudest Voice (-)	17.84%	3.18%
Average Note Duration (-)	68.67%	47.15%
Note Density (+)	63.59%	40.44%
Variability of Note Duration (-)	57.4%	32.94%
Initial Tempo (+)	55.52%	30.82%
Average Time Between Attacks (-)	55.32%	30.6%
Variability of Time Between Attacks (-)	54.07%	29.23%
Average Duration Accent (-)	53.81%	28.95%
Strength Strongest Rhythmic Pulse (-)	47.58%	22.64%
Number of Relatively Strong Pulses (+)	43.86%	19.24%
Strength Two Strong. Rhythmic Pulses (-)	41.69%	17.38%
Polyrhythms (-)	38.33%	14.69%
Strongest Rhythmic Pulse (+)	35.51%	12.61%
Strength Second Strong. Rhythmic Pulse (-)	27.9%	7.78%
Onset Autocorrelation (-)	26.67%	7.11%
Syncopation (-)	25.36%	6.43%
Average Meter Accent Synchrony (-)	24.15%	5.83%
Number of Strong Pulses (+)	23.64%	5.59%
Rhythm Range (-)	23.46%	5.50%
Rhythmic Variability (-)	23.02%	5.30%
Staccato Incidence (+)	35.22%	12.40%
Average Range of Glissandos (-)	17.51%	3.07%
Climax Position (+)	45.39%	20.60%
Average Melodic Complexity (+)	38.4%	14.74%
Consecutive Identical Pitches (+)	37.06%	13.73%
Climax Strength (-)	33.12%	10.97%
Repeated Notes (+)	32.85%	10.79%
Most Common Pitch Class Prevalence (+)	31.59%	9.98%
Relative Strength of Top Pitch Classes (-)	30.69%	9.42%
Amount of Arpeggiation (+)	29.74%	8.84%
Same Direction Interval (+)	27.95%	7.81%
Repeated Pitch Density (+)	24.46%	5.98%
Most Common Pitch Prevalence (+)	24.39%	5.95%
Distance Common Melodic Intervals (+)	22.61%	5.11%
Overall Pitch Direction (+)	21.78%	4.74%
Most Common Melodic Interval Prevalence (+)	21.11%	4.46%
Melodic Octaves (+)	20.32%	4.13%
Melodic Thirds (-)	18.04%	3.25%
Interval Between Strongest Pitch Classes (+)	17.89%	3.2%
Duration of Melodic Arcs (+)	17.67%	3.12%
Key mode (-)	22.13%	4.90%

TABLE II
BEST FEATURES OF EACH GROUP - AROUSAL

INSTRUMENTATION String Ensemble Woodwinds Acoustic Grand Piano Acoustic Guitar (nylon) Harp Choir Aahs English horn Flute Pad (warm) TEXTURE Small number of pitched and unpitched instruments Spectral texture MFCC 12 RHYTHM Low tempo High note duration Low time between attacks Low note density Small number of relatively strong pulses Strongest pulses High variability of note duration High variability of time between attacks Syncopation High rhythmic range Onset autocorrelation High duration accent Meter accent synchrony Polyrhythms Rhythmic looseness Rhythmic variability DYNAMICS Legato Glissando Vibrato MELODY Simple melody Pitch density repetition Strength of top pitches and pitch classes HARMONY Minor mode Strong tonal center Low arousal	INSTRUMENTATION Percussion Saxophone Brass Electric guitar Electric instrument Electric bass (finger) Synth bass Tremolo strings Orchestra hit Polysynth TEXTURE Large number of pitched and unpitched instruments Variability of unpitched instruments Spectral texture MFCC 2, 4, 5, 8 and 11 RHYTHM High tempo Low note duration Low time between attacks High note density Low variability of note duration Low variability of time between attacks Low rhythmic range Low duration accent Large number of strong pulses DYNAMICS Staccato MELODY Complex melody Distant melodic climax position Repeated notes Stability of melodic direction Consecutive identical pitches Arpeggiation Distant common melodic intervals Prevalence of common pitch class, pitch and melodic interval Distant strongest pitch classes HARMONY Major mode High arousal
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Fig. 4. Mappings for arousal

resulted. The correlation and determination coefficients for training on the whole set were, respectively, 74.95% and 56.17%. 8-fold cross validation of classification resulted in correlation and determination coefficients of, respectively, 71.5% and 51.12%. Valence is calculated by the weighted sum of the best features: $-0.41 \cdot \text{average note duration} + 0.17 \cdot \text{dominant spread} + 0.41 \cdot \text{initial tempo} - 0.18 \cdot \text{key mode} + 0.24 \cdot \text{climax position}$.

Correlation and determination coefficients of 56.5% and 31.92% exists between the affective labels and results obtained using the weighted mappings of a preliminary experiment¹.

B. Arousal

Table II presents prediction results by groups of features for arousal. From this, we can infer that rhythmic (e.g., average note duration, note density, time between attacks and variability of note duration), dynamics (e.g., staccato incidence), texture (spectral texture MFCC 4 and strength of top pitch classes), melodic (e.g., climax position and repeated notes) and instrumentation features (e.g., number of unpitched instruments and brass fraction) are relevant to the arousal of music.

We started by applying feature selection algorithms [18] to reduce the number of features and to improve classification results. From this a group of 23 features resulted. The correlation and determination coefficients for training on the whole set were, respectively, 90.31% and 81.55%. 8-fold cross validation of classification resulted in correlation and determination coefficients of, respectively, 84.14% and 70.79%. After this we manually selected the best group of features to know the most important features in the stage of selection, but also for the

INSTRUMENTATION String Ensemble Orchestral Strings Woodwinds Acoustic Grand Piano Pizzicato Strings Orchestral Harp Timpani Tuba French Horn English Horn Bassoon Flute Ocarina Banjo TEXTURE Small number of pitched and unpitched instruments Spectral texture MFCC 12 RHYTHM Low tempo Low note duration High time between attacks Low note density Small number of relatively strong pulses Polyrhythms Rhythmic variability Strongest pulses High variability of note duration High variability of time between attacks DYNAMICS Legato MELODY Simple melody HARMONY Minor mode Low valence	INSTRUMENTATION Acoustic Guitar Electric Guitar Electric Instrument Marimba Xylophone Accordion Fretless Bass Synth Brass Polysynth Steel Drums Saxophone TEXTURE Large number of pitched and unpitched instruments Spectral texture MFCC 4, 6, 7 and 8 RHYTHM High tempo Low note duration Low time between attacks High note density Large number of relatively strong pulses Low variability of note duration Low variability of time between attacks Meter accent synchrony DYNAMICS Staccato MELODY Large interval between strongest pitch classes Distant melodic climax position Complex melody Consecutive identical pitches HARMONY Major mode High valence
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Fig. 5. Mappings for valence

stage of transformation. From this a group of 4 features resulted. The correlation and determination coefficients for training on the whole set were, respectively, 83.86% and 70.32%. 8-fold cross validation of classification resulted in correlation and determination coefficients of, respectively, 79.14% and 62.63%. Arousal is calculated by the weighted sum of the best features: $-0.56 \cdot \text{average note duration} + 0.24 \cdot \text{initial tempo} + 0.11 \cdot \text{climax position} + 0.37 \cdot \text{consecutive identical pitches} + 0.58 \cdot \text{note density}$.

Correlation and determination coefficients of 76.58% and 58.64% exists between the affective labels and results obtained using the weighted mappings of a preliminary experiment¹.

VI. DISCUSSION

From this work much information was obtained. Fig. 4 and 5 illustrate how specific types of musical features can be changed to shift, respectively, the arousal and valence of music. For instance, a decrease in the duration of notes contribute to a decrease of both arousal and valence. Fig. 6 presents the mean of important features for each quadrant (e.g., high valence and low arousal). All this information is stored in the knowledge base and will be used in the next stage of our work that deals with the transformation of music affective content (Fig. 1).

With similar goals to [5] [10], we have developed a regression model (knowledge base) with relations between music features and emotions, Kuo et al. developed an affinity graph and Muyuan and Naiyao a SVM classifier. We used continuous dimensions (valence and arousal) instead of discrete emotions ([5] [10]). The results of our model ($\approx 90\%$) surpass the results of Kuo et al. ($\approx 80\%$) and Muyuan and Naiyao for valence ($\approx 70\%$) when using a higher number of features (≈ 20).

Average note duration - 0.2317 Dominant spread - 2.6364 Tempo - 116 Key mode - 1.5455 Climax position - 0.6018 Consecutive identical pitches - 9.8583 Note density - 24.4965 Spectral texture MFCC 4 - 0.0579 Average time between attacks - 0.1725 Variability of note duration - 0.2669 Variability of time between attacks - 0.0803 Note prevalence fretless bass - 0 String ensemble fraction - 0.0171 Saxophone fraction - 0.0275 Spectral texture MFCC 2 - 20.7700 Average duration accent - 0.7496 Polyrythms - 0.3200 Staccato incidence - 0.3812 Repeated notes - 0.2589 Average melodic complexity - 5.3439 Most common pitch class prevalence - 0.3710 Valence	Average note duration - 0.2860 Dominant spread - 3.6522 Tempo - 136.9565 Key mode - 1.1957 Climax position - 0.5595 Consecutive identical pitches - 7.4042 Note density - 26.8814 Spectral texture MFCC 4 - -0.1619 Average time between attacks - 0.1438 Variability of note duration - 0.3314 Variability of time between attacks - 0.0780 Note prevalence fretless bass - 0.0198 String ensemble fraction - 0.0638 Saxophone fraction - 0.0336 Spectral texture MFCC 2 - 17.4915 Average duration accent - 0.7740 Polyrythms - 0.4234 Staccato incidence - 0.2614 Repeated notes - 0.2015 Average melodic complexity - 5.5016 Most common pitch class prevalence - 0.2929
Average note duration - 0.9721 Dominant spread - 3.4231 Tempo - 80.3077 Key mode - 1.5385 Climax position - 0.4247 Consecutive identical pitches - 3.9058 Note density - 11.1158 Spectral texture MFCC 4 - -2.1943 Average time between attacks - 0.3116 Variability of note duration - 1.3209 Variability of time between attacks - 0.2322 Note prevalence fretless bass - 0.0083 String ensemble fraction - 0.1818 Saxophone fraction - 0 Spectral texture MFCC 2 - 9.9105 Average duration accent - 0.8123 Polyrythms - 0.5567 Staccato incidence - 0.1441 Repeated notes - 0.1016 Average melodic complexity - 5.0149 Most common pitch class prevalence - 0.2546 Arousal	Average note duration - 0.5089 Dominant spread - 4.2308 Tempo - 106.3846 Key mode - 1.3846 Climax position - 0.4674 Consecutive identical pitches - 6.7862 Note density - 15.3345 Spectral texture MFCC 4 - -1.1140 Average time between attacks - 0.1925 Variability of note duration - 0.5640 Variability of time between attacks - 0.1527 Note prevalence fretless bass - 0.0218 String ensemble fraction - 0.0531 Saxophone fraction - 0.0183 Spectral texture MFCC 2 - 14.8053 Average duration accent - 0.8013 Polyrythms - 0.5211 Staccato incidence - 0.2233 Repeated notes - 0.1518 Average melodic complexity - 5.1614 Most common pitch class prevalence - 0.2511

Fig. 6. Mean values of relevant features of musical samples for each affective quadrant

VII. CONCLUSION

We presented an extension of a previous work that undertook music emotion classification as a regression problem. SVM regression obtained the best results in the prediction and classification of the dimensions of valence and arousal. Validation results using the coefficient of determination confirmed that the prediction/classification of arousal (90.31%/81.55%) is easier than the prediction/classification of valence (89.37%/79.86%). Rhythmic (e.g., tempo, note density and average/variation of note duration), melodic (e.g., climax position and melodic complexity) and textural (e.g., spectral texture MFCCs) features proved to be very important to valence and arousal. Harmonic (e.g., key mode) and dynamics features (e.g., staccato incidence) were also important to predict, respectively, the valence and arousal. A correlation coefficient of 62.95% was obtained between valence and arousal.

With these satisfactory results, we feel ready to move to the second stage of our work, that consists in transformation of the affective content of selected music to approximate even further its affective content to an intended emotion. Both the selection and transformation will use the obtained information stored in the knowledge base (Fig. 4, 5, 6).

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